

Review article

Seismic upgrading of existing reinforced concrete buildings: A state-of-the-art review

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ABSTRACT

Collapses or serious damages of existing buildings during strong earthquakes have resulted in significant economic losses, severe injuries and loss of human lives. Given the late introduction of modern seismic standards and the large number of the existing under-designed buildings, the scientific interest has progressively been focusing on developing techniques for the seismic upgrading of existing buildings. The present paper aims at providing a review of the seismic upgrading techniques, which target reinforced concrete (RC) buildings, as such buildings constitute a large portion of the existing building stock. The retrofitting methods are divided into two distinct categories: the local measures, which enhance the behavior of individual elements and the global ones, which operate on the structure as a whole. Both traditional and novel techniques will be discussed, but the latter will be emphasized.

1. Introduction

In most regions of the developed world, the building stock has already started to age considerably. Within the European Union for example, 80% of the buildings were built before the 90's, 40% before the 60's, with a third of buildings over 50 years old [1]. The impact of the old building stock on the environment is huge as buildings are responsible for 36% of the CO₂ emissions and 40% of the total energy consumption in the EU. For this reason, the European Green Deal [2] emphasizes the need for the EU and its Member States to engage in a 'Renovation wave' of their buildings [3] and a New European Bauhaus initiative. At the same time, the strong recent earthquakes (e.g. in Southern Europe) revealed also the poor seismic resistance of the old buildings, many of which collapsed under seismic excitations resulting in significant economic losses, severe injuries and loss of human lives. As a result it was suggested within the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive [4] that also seismic risks should be addressed by Member States when planning long-term renovation strategies of buildings. Therefore, the lifetime extension of existing buildings should also include their seismic upgrading for the seismic-prone regions.

The introduction of modern seismic design standards (e.g. [5]) has addressed mainly the seismic safety of new buildings. At the same time, the last couple of decades, the scientific community has focused more on

the seismic risk associated with the existing buildings and proposed, developed and experimentally tested various seismic retrofitting methods, with the aim of transferring these techniques from the laboratories to the real engineering practice. Moreover, seismic standards (e.g. [6]) and guidelines (e.g. [7,8]) for the retrofitting of existing structures were published relatively recently. Their application is not yet obligatory though, except for specific cases.

Within this scope, the present paper aims at providing a thorough review of the seismic upgrading techniques, which target reinforced concrete (RC) buildings, as the latter constitute the largest portion of the existing building stock. A briefer overview for all building types was recently given in [9]. Seismic upgrading techniques can be divided in two major categories, depending on the way they "treat" the structure. At first, there are the ones that operate at the element level (Local measures) and then those that operate on the structure as a whole (Global measures). Obviously, when it comes to upgrading an actual building, various techniques can and might need to be combined, addressing its specific characteristics, so that a cost-effective strengthening scheme can be provided. Depending on their age as well as the materials employed in each technique, the seismic intervention techniques can also be further divided to conventional and novel ones.

Fig. 1 shows the goals at which a seismic retrofitting scheme might aim. When only the ductility of a structure needs to be improved, then

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local measures are typically sufficient and normally do not affect the structure’s strength and stiffness, or they affect it marginally. However, if the capacity also needs to be increased, global measures will most likely have to be employed, as achieving a much higher lateral load capacity in a structure via local measures alone would be an uneconomical option. Lastly, in cases that both the capacity and ductility of a structure are in need of improvement, then a combination of global and local measures should be employed. It is noted that in the context of this work, the terms “capacity” and “strength” are used interchangeably.

Apart from increasing a building’s lateral strength, there is also the alternative of decreasing the earthquake-induced forces, which can be achieved by reducing the mass and/or reducing the lateral stiffness of the structure. Mass reduction can be realized through the use of lighter partition walls, floor removal etc., while stiffness reduction is achieved via the employment of base isolators and energy dissipation systems, while certain energy dissipation systems (e.g. Buckling-restrained braces, see Section 3.1.1.3) may also add stiffness. Fig. 2 outlines the main categories of seismic upgrading techniques targeting RC buildings, whereas Table 1 summarizes the most common measures together with the properties they affect. Specific techniques will be thoroughly described in the next sections of this paper.

2. Local measures

The local upgrading techniques comprise measures applied to specific structural elements of a building, in order to enhance their mechanical characteristics. The general idea is to add some sort of external reinforcement to the existing beam/column/joint member and that way increase its flexural and/or shear capacity as well as its ductility. Traditional techniques make use of conventional materials like concrete and structural steel, whilst novel ones employ more innovative materials like Fiber Reinforced Polymers (FRP), Textile Reinforced Mortars (TRM) etc. In the following sections, both conventional and novel techniques will be described, putting more emphasis on the latter.

2.1. RC/mortar jacketing

The first and probably most traditional technique of seismic upgrading of RC members, is that of constructing an RC jacket around the initial element (Fig. 3), thus enlarging its sectional area and increasing both its longitudinal and transversal reinforcement. This technique can greatly increase the member’s flexural and shear capacity, as well as its ductility. Moreover, due to the increase in the dimensions and the addition of extra flexural reinforcement, the element’s bending stiffness also increases, a side-effect that might not be desirable in some cases. RC jackets of various types have been the topic of several

Fig. 2. Taxonomy of seismic upgrading techniques.

experimental studies (e.g. [10–16]) and have also have been widely used in practice in the recent past successfully.

Recently, there is a tendency to replace the concrete in such jackets with high-performance materials, due to their higher durability and better mechanical properties. Within this field, a number of concrete alternatives have been proposed and are listed below.

High-performance, fiber-reinforced cementitious composite mortars (HPFRCC) may be used for the strengthening of the critical region of RC columns, even when they are corrosion-damaged. Such schemes can result in a significant reduction in shear and bending cracks, an overall enhancement of the force–displacement behavior, better energy dissipation and less stiffness degradation [17,18]. The use of self-compacting ultra-high-performance fiber-reinforced concrete (UHPRFC) in RC columns with insufficient lap slices, has also been found to eliminate bond failure and damage in the plastic hinge regions [19]. Other studies employed jackets made of ferro-cement [20], engineered cementitious

Fig. 1. Seismic retrofitting goals.

Table 1
Effect of local and global retrofit measures on building properties (partially based on [98]).

	Technique	Strength	Stiffness	Ductility	Irregularity	Force demand	Deformation demand
Local measures	RC/mortar jacketing	+	+	+		-	+
	Steel jacketing	+		+			
	FRP/TRM jacketing	+		+			
	Hybrid jackets	+		+			
Global measures	Bracing systems	+	+		+	-	+
	Shear walls	+	+		+	-	+
	Infills	+	+		+	-	+
	Mass reduction				+	+	-
	Seismic isolation			-	+	+	+
	Energy dissipation systems			+/-			+

Fig. 3. Seismic upgrading with RC jacketing [Source: Courtesy C. Chrysostomou, TUC].

composites (ECC) [21] and high-strength micro-concrete [22].

The seismic upgrading of RC members with RC or other high-performance cementitious mortar jacket has proved itself over the years both in the lab and in practice. The most important benefits and drawbacks of this family of strengthening techniques are summarized below:

- + Significant increase in strength and ductility.
- + Adaptable to any shape of section.
- + Makes use of materials that both engineers and workers are familiar with.
- Expensive, labor intensive and time-consuming method.
- Significant occupancy disruption.
- Loss in floor area due to the increase of the cross section sizes.

- Modification of the stiffness of the member.
- Use of large quantities of materials (i.e. concrete and steel) with high environmental burden (higher embodied CO2 emissions, more energy in manufacturing).

2.2. Steel jacketing

Instead of RC or other cementitious materials, structural steel can be used as external reinforcement to enhance the behavior of existing RC elements (Fig. 4). A combination of steel angles and plates can be used to form a cage around an RC element, thus increasing its flexural and shear strength, but also its ductility and stiffness [23,24]. Alternatively, tubed steel elements or sheets can be wrapped around elements to provide

Fig. 4. Seismic upgrading with steel jacketing.

extra confinement to the inner concrete and that way increase its ductility and shear capacity [25,26]. In the latter case, the volume between the added steel and the existing concrete may be filled with grout.

Recently, Fakharifar et al. [27] suggested a technique for the rapid repair of severely damaged circular RC columns using lightweight, prestressed steel jackets. This scheme consists of a thin steel sheet, wrapped around the RC element and restrained from buckling via the employment of several prestressed strands. The retrofitting process can be carried out by a group of two workers in less than 12 h and does not modify the initial column's geometry. The method was able to restore the strength and ductility of the tested members to 115% and 140%, respectively; their stiffness though was not fully restored, approaching though 84% of the undamaged column's stiffness.

More recently, Wang et al. [28] recommended an innovative approach for the seismic strengthening of rectangular RC columns, which support very high axial loads (normalized axial loads of ~ 0.6). In this method, pre-cambered steel plates are applied on the opposite faces of the member and then post-compressed by tying them tightly together with anchor bolts. That way, through this pre-compression process, part of the axial load is transferred from the column to the new steel elements, relieving the former significantly. The experimental study showed that the strengthened columns can maintain their shear-carrying capacity under high axial loads and also exhibit significantly increased ductility, which can be fine-tuned by controlling the thickness and/or the initial pre-camber of the steel plates.

Upgrading RC elements with steel jacketing techniques is a less popular method in engineering practice, but it can still provide excellent solutions in specific cases. The most important strengths and weaknesses of steel jacketing related methods are summarized below:

- + Significant increase in strength and ductility.
- + Makes use of materials that both engineers and workers are familiar with.
 - Relatively expensive, labor intensive and time-consuming method*.
 - Occupancy disruption*.
 - Need for corrosion protection.
 - Modification of the stiffness of the member and addition of significant extra weight*.

(* These drawbacks are less significant in comparison to RC jacketing)

2.3. FRP jacketing

Probably the most popular technique for the seismic retrofitting of individual RC elements involves the use of fiber-reinforced polymers (FRP). When compared to traditional retrofitting methods, FRP are a very competitive alternative, as they offer ease and speed of installation, less labor work, minimum geometric changes, very high strength to weight ratio and minimum occupancy disruption (e.g. [29]). On the other side, they exhibit very poor behavior when exposed to high temperatures, in which case they need protection, and demand high quality work to be performed by experienced personnel. Yet, in the (not so common) case of open jackets (e.g. U-shaped jackets in T-beams), the effective utilization of the high strength of FRP may be low (e.g. in the order of 35%), due to the fact that debonding failures precede the material failures. The use of spike anchors increases the utilization of FRP tensile strength (see Section 2.3.2).

2.3.1. Fiber types

Fibers in FRP materials can be of various types. The most usual fiber type used in seismic retrofitting applications is carbon (CFRP), due to its high elastic modulus and excellent durability; however, it is the most expensive material as well. A lower cost choice is to use glass fibers (GFRP), however as glass has roughly 1/3 of carbon fibers' elasticity modulus, larger material quantities need to be applied. Other fiber types that can be used (but are not common) are aramid, basalt, polyester,

polyparaphenylene benzobisoxazole (PBO) and polyethylene terephthalate (PET). Lastly, it is also possible to form hybrid FRP by combining two or more materials together. Typical stress-strain curves for various types of fibers are given in Fig. 5.

2.3.2. Strengthening methods

2.3.2.1. General. FRP are normally used in the field of RC member strengthening as externally bonded reinforcement (EBR) and can be applied (typically) in two distinct ways. The first and most frequent is to use FRP in the form of fabrics (Fig. 6) and attach them to the concrete substrate using epoxy resins. This way, they can be used as shear reinforcement in beams and columns with insufficient stirrups in order to ensure a ductile flexural response. Moreover, when wrapped around columns they provide confinement to the inner concrete and that way significantly increase the section's ductility. The application of fabrics is possible on simple cross section shapes (circular or rectangular with low aspect ratio) as well as on more complicated shapes (e.g. T, L, rectangular with high aspect ratio) through the use of anchors.

Alternatively, and rather rarely in seismic retrofitting, FRPs can be used in the form of prefabricated laminates, strips or bars (Fig. 7) to act as external longitudinal or transverse reinforcement in existing elements and thus increase their flexural or shear capacity. Their application can be either external, on the faces of an RC member, or inside grooves, in which case we have the near surface mounted (NSM) method. It should be emphasized though, that when used as external flexural reinforcement, strengthened members do achieve higher flexural strengths, but lower deformation capacities as fibers fail (or debond) at significantly lower strains than reinforcing steel (e.g. see Fig. 5). Strengthening and seismic retrofitting solutions with FRP are summarized in Fig. 8.

2.3.2.2. Seismic retrofitting with FRP. When it comes to seismic retrofitting, FRP have been proved to be most effective when used in the form of sheets as shear reinforcement or as a means to provide extra confinement. A review on seismic retrofitting of RC with FRP is given in [29] and a more detailed treatment on the subject is presented in [30] and [8]. A few of the numerous other studies are summarized below.

Ma et al. [31] have observed that when shear-deficient RC columns are wrapped with CFRP, they exhibit stable flexural behavior, as is they can sustain numerous loading/unloading cycles with no or little strength loss. In their studies, the external reinforcement acted similarly to classical steel hoops, preventing shear-type failures and confining the inner concrete section, thus greatly increasing the section's available ductility. In the studies of Sause et al. [32], Ghobarah and Galal [33] and Haroun and Elsanadedy [34-35] it was also found that ductility was increased, column failure was delayed and that buckling of longitudinal bars could be avoided through the use of stiffer CFRP jackets. Comparable results were reported by Balsamo et al. [36] who employed a combination of CFRP sheets and laminates to seismically strengthen a full-scale RC frame.

Similar enhancement in seismic behavior has also been observed in RC members strengthened with GFRP jackets. Sheikh and Yau [37], Memon and Sheikh [38] and Youm et al. [39] have reported that GFRP wrapping improves the ductility, energy dissipation and capacity of RC columns, as well as the seismic performance of RC columns with insufficient lap slices.

Bousias et al. [40] studied the efficiency of CFRP versus GFRP jacketing on RC columns with or without corroded reinforcement. It was found that, for the same circumferential stiffness (FRP elasticity modulus times the jacket thickness), the effectiveness was the same. The same conclusion was also made by [41], regarding the stiffness being the decisive factor.

Concerning the cross-sectional geometry of the RC elements, Abdel-Moody et al. [42,43] found that confinement was most effective in circular sections, followed by square and then rectangular. This

Fig. 5. Typical σ - ϵ curves for various types of fibers.

Fig. 6. Wrapping of RC (a) columns and (b) beams with CFRP; (c) wrapping of RC shear wall with GFRP [Source: Lecture notes, T. Triantafillou].

Fig. 7. (a) Flexural and shear strengthening with FRP laminates; (b) flexural strengthening with NSM reinforcement [Source: Lecture notes, T. Triantafillou].

effectiveness was reduced in case the elements had already sustained some damage.

Harries et al. [44], Harajli and Dagher [45] and Harajli [46] examined the behavior of CFRP reinforced RC columns with lap slices. In their studies, they observed that the jackets improved significantly the bond

strength of the spliced bars. This in turn resulted in higher capacity and ductility, but also lower pinching effect and bond deterioration.

In the studies by Ozcan et al. [47,48] it was also observed that the rotation capacity and energy dissipation of CFRP retrofitted columns was increased. At the same time, the stiffness degradation was

Fig. 8. FRP strengthening roadmap.

significantly reduced. Colomb et al. [49] studied the efficacy of continuous and discontinuous FRP wraps and concluded that the former are characterized by flexural failure while the latter exhibited a mixed flexure-shear behavior.

Pantelides et al. [50] showed that CFRP jacketing is an effective rehabilitation measure for improving the seismic performance of existing beam-column joints with inadequate seismic details in terms of increased joint shear strength and inelastic rotation capacity.

Prestressing has also been employed in combination with FRP jacketing, e.g. in the work by Zhou et al. [51], in order to overcome the stress hysteresis of FRP sheets relatively to the inner concrete. An overall improvement in terms of seismic performance was observed, as load capacity, ductility and energy dissipation increased.

Vrettos et al. [52] used carbon fiber spike-anchors as a means of anchoring longitudinally applied FRP fabrics in the form of externally applied flexural reinforcement for columns. The anchor efficacy was found to be almost linearly analogous to their weight; the higher the volume of fibers in each anchor, the higher the tensile strength it can carry. The tensile capacity of carbon fiber spike-anchors in connecting the column flexural (longitudinal) FRP reinforcement to the foundation block was also investigated by Bournas et al. [53]. It was confirmed that the carbon fiber spike-anchor is an effective anchorage system, which could be used in a range of strengthening applications including the seismic upgrading of RC columns. Pohoryles et al. [54] proposed the use of carbon fibre strands for the flexural strengthening of columns for eliminating single-storey mechanisms in RC frames.

Choi et al. [55] retrofitted RC columns with and without lap slices using tensioned GFRP winding wires. They observed that with this retrofitting method flexural capacity and drift at failure were increased, while at the same time, buckling of the longitudinal reinforcement, concrete spalling and splitting of the lap slices were prevented.

A comparative study was recently carried out by Yang and Wang [56] to assess the effectiveness of full CFRP versus strap CFRP wrapping as external reinforcement in shear-controlled RC columns. The retrofitted columns showed increased shear capacity and ductility, which dropped with higher axial loads. The authors concluded that, for the same volumetric ratio, CFRP straps were more efficient than full wrapping. Wang et al. [28] also examined the same problem for high-strength RC columns. Nonetheless, they observed that full wrapping of the

elements would result in in better behavior.

Dai et al. [57] employed large fracture strain polyethylene terephthalate (PET) FRP and compared them to aramid FRP (AFRP). The tests they conducted on RC specimens showed that PET FRP increases the ductility significantly and does not rupture at the ultimate limit state, making itself an interesting alternative to conventional FRP. Liu and Li [58] recently compared the efficiency of conventional CFRP versus PET FRP on partially corroded columns. They reported that PET FRP exhibited similar performance with regard to the enhancement of their seismic behavior in terms of energy dissipation, damping ratio, hysteretic performance and stiffness degradation.

Chang et al. [13] used polyester FRP sheets for strengthening RC columns with insufficient reinforcement. In their study, retrofitted specimens showed ductile behavior, along with significantly increased energy dissipation.

Ouyang et al. [59] used basalt FRP (BFRP) and compared them to CFRP, applied on RC columns. Their results showed that BFRP retrofitted columns exhibited the same or even better performance than those retrofitted with CFRP. Taking also into account that BFRP sheets cost about one-fifth the price of CFRP sheets, the authors concluded that they are a competitive alternative.

2.4. TRM jacketing

Fiber Reinforced Polymers have been used widely over the last years as a means to achieve better seismic behavior in deficient RC elements, mainly columns. However, apart from their advantages related to their application in retrofitting schemes, FRP entail a number of problems, which are listed below [60]:

- Resins behave poorly in high temperatures (above their glass transition temperature T_g), therefore the FRP reinforcement needs to be protected if it has to stay active during a fire.
- Epoxy resins are expensive.
- Application of resins has to be made on clean, dry surfaces, within regular temperatures and by experienced workers, as they are hazardous materials.

- In case of wrapped elements, the final product is vapor impermeable, due to the zero porosity of the resins, something that may cause damage to the concrete below.
- It is difficult to conduct a post-earthquake assessment of a strengthened element, as the FRP jacket will “hide” any damage suffered by the inner concrete.

A possible solution to address the above-mentioned issues is to use the same fibrous materials (carbon, glass, basalt etc.) in the form of textiles embedded in cementitious mortars, instead of fabrics impregnated in epoxy resins. These textiles are essentially fabric meshes made of long woven, knitted, or even unwoven fiber rovings in at least two (typically orthogonal) directions. The density (quantity and spacing) of rovings in each direction can be controlled independently, thus affecting the mechanical characteristics of the textile and the degree of penetration of the mortar matrix through the mesh.

The end material is called Textile Reinforced Mortar (TRM), but it can also be found in the literature by other names, such as Textile Reinforced Concrete (TRC) or Fiber Reinforced Cementitious Matrix (FRCM). TRM have demonstrated superior performance than FRP as strengthening materials at high temperatures (e.g. [61–64]), whereas the TRM mechanical behaviour has also been found satisfactory after exposure to fire [65,66]. Fig. 9 shows the application of TRM in RC columns and beams, respectively.

As far as confinement is concerned, Triantafyllou et al. [60] conducted a set of axial compression experiments using concrete cylinders and short rectangular columns, confined with TRM. They reported that TRM jackets can provide a substantial gain in the compressive strength as well as deformation capacity of concrete cylinders, with that gain being higher as the number of the confining layers increases. They also compared the efficiency of TRM jackets versus resin-impregnated (i.e. FRP) textile jackets and found that the former were only slightly inferior to the latter with respect to strength and ultimate deformation. Similar results were drawn from the tests on short rectangular columns, in which the performance of TRM was found to be very close to that of equivalent FRP jackets. Lastly, it was observed that the failure of TRM jackets was less abrupt than that of resin-impregnated textile jackets, a phenomenon that was attributed to the slowly progressing fracture of individual fiber bundles.

Bournas et al. [67] studied the effectiveness of TRM jackets as a means of confining RC columns with limited capacity and compared them to FRP jackets. A significant increase was again observed in terms of both strength and ultimate deformation. Moreover, when compared to FRP jackets of equal stiffness, TRM jackets were found to be slightly less effective (by about 10%) in terms of increasing strength and deformation capacity. Cyclic uniaxial flexure tests on large-scale RC columns showed that TRM jackets are very effective as a means of

increasing the cyclic deformation capacity and the energy dissipation of old-type RC columns with poor detailing, by delaying bar buckling. Therefore, they concluded that TRM jacketing has practically the same effectiveness as FRP jackets of the same stiffness and strength.

In a subsequent study, Bournas et al. [68] investigated the effectiveness of TRM jackets in confining RC columns with limited capacity due to bar buckling or bond failure at lap splice regions. Experimental results indicated that TRM jacketing was quite effective as a means of increasing the cyclic deformation capacity of old-type RC columns with poor detailing, by delaying bar buckling and by preventing splitting bond failures in columns with lap-spliced bars. Compared with their FRP counterparts, the TRM jackets were found to be equally effective in terms of increasing both the strength and deformation capacity of the retrofitted columns. An in-depth experimental investigation as well as an analytical model for columns with lap-splices is given in Bournas and Triantafyllou [69], whereas an in-depth analytical investigation of the problem of bar buckling is presented in Bournas and Triantafyllou [70].

As far as shear strengthening is concerned, Triantafyllou and Papanicolaou [71] tested shear-dominated RC members, strengthened with closed TRM jackets. The jackets were effective in transforming the failure mechanism from shear to flexural and that way prevent a brittle response. Compared to FRP jackets, the authors stated that the TRM strengthening system was about 55% as effective.

Tetta et al. [72–74] explored systematically the shear strengthening of RC beams with TRM jackets, investigating the TRM vs FRP jacketing in side-bonding, U-wrapping and full-wrapping, different number of the strengthening layers and the effect of the shear span-to-depth ratio in beams strengthened in shear with U-shaped TRM jackets. They concluded that the TRM is generally less effective than FRP in increasing the shear capacity of concrete; however the effectiveness depends on both the strengthening configuration and the number of layers. U-wrapping strengthening configuration is much more effective than side-bonding in case of TRM jackets and the effectiveness of TRM jackets increases considerably with increasing the number of layers. It was also concluded that the shear span-to-depth ratio has no effect on neither the failure mode nor the contribution of the TRM jacket to the total shear resistance of the beams.

Tzoura and Triantafyllou [75] did a large set of cyclic loading tests experiments on RC T-beams strengthened in shear using U-shaped TRM jackets. Mechanical anchors through the RC slab were also used to provide end anchorage to the jacket. In this study, it was concluded that the jacket effectiveness increases substantially when steel anchors are employed and that high strains can be achieved in the TRM. Moreover, it was stated that TRM U-jackets are nearly as effective as FRP U-jackets in increasing the shear capacity of RC T-beams.

Tetta et al. [76] tested 10 full-scale RC T-beams strengthened in shear with TRM jackets and textile-based anchors. Their study

(a)

(b)

Fig. 9. Applications of TRM jacketing on RC (a) column and (b) beam.

concluded that: (1) the use of textile-based anchors increases dramatically the effectiveness of TRM U-jackets; (2) increasing the number of layers in non-anchored jackets results in an almost proportional increase of the shear capacity; and (c) TRM jackets can be as effective as FRP jackets in increasing the shear capacity of full-scale RC T-beams.

A simple design method for the calculation of the contribution of TRM jacketing to the total shear resistance of RC beams is presented by Tetta et al. [73,74]. The method predicts reliably the expected failure mode in a TRM system based on the characteristics of its textile reinforcement and the mortar properties.

A detailed treatment of TRM and their use in seismic retrofitting can be found in Koutas et al. [77].

2.5. Hybrid jacketing systems

Via the concurrent employment of different strengthening techniques, a more efficient retrofitting scheme can be designed and achieved. The next sections present the main developments on this subject during the last years.

2.5.1. FRP/TRM jackets with NSM reinforcement

The most common hybrid method found in the literature is the combination of FRP/TRM jackets with NSM strips. These systems result in flexural and shear strengthening, as well as in confinement, without affecting the member's dimensions.

Wu et al. [78] embedded GFRP bars into the plastic hinge zone of RC columns combined with normal CFRP jackets. The bars were perpendicular to the member axis with the purpose of expanding the effectively confined zone. They observed that concrete failure was suppressed and rebar buckling was prevented, thus increasing the members' ductility and energy dissipation by a factor of three.

Bournas and Triantafillou [79] strengthened RC columns using different types of NSM materials (FRP and stainless steel) combined with TRM jackets (Fig. 10). They reported that NSM FRP or steel are effective in increasing a member's flexural strength, by a factor of up to two, without diversely affecting its deformation capacity. Moreover, it was observed that the TRM jacket was very effective in controlling the buckling of the NSM bars, thus allowing them to reach high strains until

failure. Subsequently, Bournas and Triantafillou [80] presented an analytical model for the analysis of RC columns strengthened in flexure with NSM reinforcement and confined with TRM jackets for cross-sections subjected to biaxial bending combined with axial loading.

Sarafraz and Danesh [81] also used NSM FRP in combination with CFRP jackets and reported a significant increase of up to 86% in the flexural capacity of RC columns, as well as an overall improvement in the members' seismic performance. Li et al. [82] applied the same technique (NSM GFRP with CFRP jackets) and added CFRP anchors in the plastic hinge region of RC columns with cross section dimensions of high aspect ratio. They reported that NSM GFRP rebars increase the flexural strength by up to 51%, while CFRP jackets with CFRP anchors increase both the strength and ductility of columns by 27% and 72% respectively.

Napoli and Realfonzo [83] combined NSM longitudinal rebars into grooves cut into RC columns with steel angles; then they wrapped the whole system with CFRP jackets. The authors observed a significant increase in the members' flexural strength and deformation capacity by up to 60% and 30% respectively.

FRP jackets have also been combined with NSM FRP other than glass or carbon. Seyhan et al. [84] used aramid FRP and were able to achieve up to 90% higher flexural strength, as well as satisfactory drifts of 3%. Similarly, Fahmy and Wu [85] as well as Jiang et al. [86] used basalt FRP and obtained very good results in terms of both flexural capacity and ductility.

Seifi et al. [87] used NSM steel rebars and GFRP in combination with CFRP jackets, to strengthen deficient RC columns, which were under-reinforced with plain bars and had insufficient lap slices. Significant improvements were reported for the flexural strength (two times higher), energy dissipation (more than three times higher) and hysteretic damping (two times higher). The use of steel rebars over GFRP as NSM reinforcement led to approximately 10% higher lateral strengths and 16% higher drifts.

Recently, Shin et al. [88] studied experimentally the seismic behavior of non-ductile building frames retrofitted with the NSM-FRP hybrid system. The full-scale dynamic testing was performed on the retrofitted test frame to realistically measure dynamic responses and quantify the retrofit effects. The hybrid retrofit system reduced the peak

Fig. 10. (a) NSM strips combined with (b) TRM jacketing.
Source: [79]

inter-story drift of the first-story columns by about 25% and their hinge rotation by approximately 76%. Additionally, the retrofit system uniformly distributed the damage or drift over the entire structure.

2.5.2. FRP and steel jacketing

The combination of CFRP jackets with steel elements was first examined by Realfonzo and Napoli [89], who used steel angles together with FRP wraps to strengthen RC columns. It was concluded that a great improvement in the flexural response can be achieved (up to two times higher), provided that the steel angles are anchored in the foundation of the RC elements. Li et al. [90] combined CFRP and steel jackets in order to enhance the seismic behavior of corrosion-damaged RC columns. They reported that the combined use of CFRP and steel was more effective in improving the strength and ductility of a member, than the use of only one material. Furthermore, according to their work, the higher the degree of corrosion or the axial load, the more noticeable the strengthening effect; an up to 50% strength increase and four times higher deformation capacity were achieved.

ElSouri and Harajli [91] studied the seismic performance of RC columns with lap slices, strengthened with steel ties as well as FRP jackets externally. They reported that retrofitted elements withstood up to 60% higher lateral loads and drifts, dissipated more energy and experienced less damage.

Chou et al. [92] strengthened RC columns using a corrugated steel tube wrapped with GFRP sheets, in order to create a ribbed surface between the concrete substrate and the FRP jacket. They reported that, by adding extra GFRP sheets, the failure mode changed from shear to flexural; also this system increased significantly the drift capacity by almost six times, as well as the energy dissipation.

In order to retrofit corrosion-damaged RC bridge columns, Afshin et al. [93] suggested a composite steel (inside) – CFRP (outside) jacket. They reported an improvement in the energy dissipation and the strength degradation characteristics of the response, but they did not observe any significant improvement in the ductility.

2.5.3. Steel/FRP and high-performance materials

Repair/strengthening and/or seismic retrofitting of damaged RC elements has been achieved by combining composites with high-performance cementitious mortars. Ma and Li [94] repaired damaged RC columns using fast curing early-strength cement mortar along with basalt FRP and reported a significant improvement in both energy dissipation (by around 50%) and ductility (by two times). The flexural strength of moderately damaged elements was fully restored; when the damage was more severe though, a full capacity restoration could not be achieved.

Xue et al. [95] combined high-performance fiber-reinforced (steel or polymer fibers) concrete (HPFRC) with steel rebars to repair severely damaged RC bridge columns. This technique was not only able to fully restore the member's strength, stiffness and ductility, but also increased its energy dissipation by around 30%; HPFRC with steel fibers was more efficient with respect to that matter.

Cho et al. [96] used high-performance fiber-reinforced cementitious composite (HPFRCC) sprayed mortar together with steel bars in order to enhance the seismic behavior of under-reinforced RC columns, typical of old constructions. They performed cyclic lateral loading tests, which showed that the retrofitting technique was effective in increasing the columns' lateral strength by 20% and achieving a many times higher deformation capacity, by altering the failure mode from shear to flexure. Cracking was also reduced, and higher energy dissipation was observed.

Recently, Rajput et al. [97] repaired corrosion-damaged RC columns with HPFRC in combination with GFRP jackets. They reported that the performance of the retrofitted columns was adequate in terms of restoring the member's load capacity, but it could not satisfy the ductility demands, posed by modern regulations.

3. Global measures

When a drastic increase in the lateral load capacity or the stiffness of a structure is needed, it is very likely that local retrofitting measures alone either would not suffice or would demand such extended interventions that the final retrofitting scheme would become uneconomical. In such cases, global measures are employed, aiming at either increasing the structure's lateral strength and stiffness or decreasing the seismic demand. The former is usually achieved by adding new structural elements to the existing building, thus increasing significantly its lateral stiffness and resistance. The alternative of decreasing the earthquake-induced forces to a given structure in the first place, is normally achieved through the employment of base isolation systems or energy dissipating devices (dampers). The following sections provide a state-of-the-art description of such retrofitting schemes, which are applicable to RC buildings.

3.1. Capacity increase

3.1.1. Addition of bracing systems

An effective way to increase a building's stiffness and strength characteristics is by adding a bracing system within selected frames. The new elements can be tailored to take up the lateral loads almost entirely, but since they have to work in conjunction with the existing frame members, great care must be paid to their connections to the frame elements as well as to the increased axial loads, which will be induced to the columns. Furthermore, as the retrofitting works are normally done on the outside frames of the structure, the loss in living space area and the occupancy disruption are minimal. A number of different bracing types exist and can be employed to RC structures. The most usual is that of concentric bracing (Fig. 11a), in which the horizontal seismic forces are resisted by axially loaded members. Alternatively, eccentric braces (Fig. 11b) resist the horizontal forces by a combination of axially loaded members and shear links, which are used as energy dissipating mechanisms.

To address the problem of buckling, which is inherent in braces, buckling-restrained braces have been developed and constitute another viable option. Last, but not least, post-tensioned rods or prestressed cables is a relatively new retrofitting scheme which can also be employed to solve buckling-related problems.

3.1.1.1. Concentric braces. Concentric braces are the most widely used type of braces for retrofitting RC frames. The high axial forces (tensile and compressive) developed in the added members resist lateral loads through their projections to the horizontal direction. Appropriate types of concentric braces that can be used for retrofitting RC buildings are diagonal bracings, X-bracings and Λ - or V-bracings. K-braces on the other side should not be used because they introduce high shear forces to the columns they converge to [98].

Experimental and analytical investigations have shown that concentric braces can significantly increase the strength and stiffness of under-designed RC frames [99–101]. Moreover, the fact that they can be attached on the external faces of a building's frames in a short period of time, makes them a very appealing retrofitting option both in terms of aesthetics but also in cases which occupancy disruption should be kept to a minimum. On the downside, concentric braces do not seem to improve the ductility of the retrofitted structure, since their mode of failure is buckling of the compressed members.

3.1.1.2. Eccentric braces. To avoid buckling of the compressed diagonal element and increase the ductility of the braces, one option is to connect them eccentrically to the surrounding frame. This is achieved using Λ -shaped braces, which are not connected directly the frame's beam, but through a shear link (e.g. Fig. 10b); a short element which is tailored to develop plastic deformations before any buckling occurs. Since all the

Fig. 11. (a) Concentric and (b) eccentric bracing systems.

damage is concentrated in this, small element, its replacement can easily be carried out in cases it has been deformed excessively.

Experimental investigations have shown that this retrofitting method can result in a considerable increase of the building's capacity (e.g. [102]). The increase in the stiffness is also important but less than in the case of concentric braces [103]. At the same time it improves its ductility and provides an effective means for energy dissipation [104–106].

3.1.1.3. Buckling-restrained braces. Eccentric braces, when designed correctly, do not exhibit buckling failure types. However, they do that in the expense of the frame's lateral stiffness, which in some cases might be necessary. A possible solution to that is to use concentric buckling-restrained braces (BRBs). BRBs consist of a steel core element, which is encased into a steel tube, filled with an unbonded material. That way, only the core element is stressed, while the outer tube provides out-of-plane stability, thus eliminating the possibility of buckling during the compression of the element.

Various research programs on BRB have been performed and shown that this retrofitting technique can effectively increase a frame's strength, stiffness and ductility at the same time. Large axial strains can be achieved without buckling occurring prematurely [107] and high ductility gains are possible as well [108]. To fully avoid buckling failure, Wada and Nakashima [109] suggested that the Euler buckling load must be 50% higher than the yield load of the element. The feasibility and effectiveness of using BRBs as a means of upgrading existing RC structures was also shown in a series of numerical studies (e.g. [110,111]).

3.1.1.4. Post-tensioned cables. The last option to avoid the buckling failure types, which are common to concentric braces, is by using post-tensioned cables instead of a traditional bracing system [7]. These cables are made of strands which are placed inside steel or PVC ducts with adequate protection against corrosion and can easily be applied on building facades and extend over more than one storey. If not prestressed at all, such cables exhibit elastic buckling upon the slightest compressive load and remain inactive (and undamaged) until the load reverses and tension is induced to them. If they are prestressed though, they are also active when "compressed" and thus able to contribute to the lateral resistance of the structure. At the same time though, the higher the amount of prestress, the lower the margin until tensile yielding occurs, leading to larger accumulation of inelastic strains and loss of prestress.

Prestressing forces of 20% to 75% of the cable yield force have been reported [112–114]. It is important to note that in case of high initial prestress, the prestressing forces exhibit significant time-dependent losses (mainly due to cable relaxation) and therefore the cables must be re-tensioned periodically. Last, but not least, since pretensioning induces axial compression in the RC columns, it might be necessary to strengthen them using some jacketing technique (see section 2). That way, the adverse effect of high axial load on their ductility can be mitigated.

3.1.1.5. Steel plate shear walls. The use of metal Steel Plate Shear Walls

(SPSWs) (or shear panels) for the seismic retrofitting of existing RC structures was examined by Formisano et al. [115]. Slender steel panels were inserted in both frames of the ground floor of an existing building, which was tested on site. The panels were bolted on steel elements, which were then connected firmly to the beam and foundation of the RC frame, thus providing the composite action. An impressive, ten-fold increase of the lateral strength was observed, with the respective stiffness being double that of the initial structure.

Since SPSWs can achieve a significant strength increase, it might also be necessary to strengthen the boundary RC members in order to withstand the higher stresses transferred to them. To avoid such costly interventions, Formisano et al. [116] proposed the use of perforated SPSWs to fine-tune the amount of the extra strength added through the system. Numerical simulations showed that drilling percentages of 40% and 60% of the plate area could provide significant cost savings of 16% and 27%, without excessively compromising the strength and stiffness of the retrofitted structure.

3.1.1.6. Steel exoskeletons. A recently proposed retrofitting scheme for RC frames involves the application of diagonal grids ("diagrids") from the outside of existing RC buildings, in the form of a 3D lattice structure, called exoskeleton (Fig. 12). Diagrid diagonal members are designed to intersect at floors, where they are connected to steel horizontal ring beams, which have the double function to stabilize the diagrid exoskeleton and to collect and transfer the seismic forces from the building floor diaphragms to the diagrid and to a new foundation system. Diagrid exoskeletons may be combined with thermal insulation, to offer integrated solutions for combined seismic and energy retrofitting (e.g. [117,118]).

Instead of diagrids, external steel concentric braces may be employed across selected frames to upgrade the seismic performance of existing RC

Fig. 12. Concept of the diagrid exoskeleton [Source: Courtesy A. Marini, Univ. Bergamo].

buildings. Formisano et al. [119] explored this idea through case studies, performed on a four-storey reference building, which was designed for gravity loads only. Three variations of the structure were taken into account; one with bare frames, one with infilled frames and one with a pilotis configuration. Four frames were braced along the perimeter of the structure, one in each of its four sides. In all three cases, the bracing system was able to significantly improve the seismic behavior of the initial structure, as the capacity to demand displacement ratios increased up to four times. A comprehensive review for external steel bracing systems can be found in [120].

3.1.2. Addition of RC shear walls

The addition of new RC shear walls is an alternative to using steel braces as lateral load resisting mechanisms. The new elements are also designed to resist the majority of seismic loads so that the existing elements only play a secondary role. RC shear walls are very effective in reducing inter-storey drifts, mitigating irregularities and preventing soft-storey failure mechanisms.

3.1.2.1. New shear walls. New shear walls can be constructed around an existing column, on the external side of a selected frame or externally of the building as buttresses (see Fig. 13). It is very important that the new elements be properly connected to the structure as well as adequately supported to the ground with new, strong foundations. Research has shown that this retrofitting method can significantly increase a building's strength and stiffness [121–123].

3.1.2.2. RC infilling of bays. Shear walls can also be constructed within existing RC frames, thus creating an infill with considerably higher lateral strength and stiffness. Connection of the new element with the surrounding frame has to be provided using shear dowels and its foundation should also be carefully dimensioned, as in the case of new shear walls.

One of the first studies was performed by Aoyama et al. [124], who conducted tests on one storey RC frames to examine the influence of the amount of vertical reinforcement, the type of connection to the surrounding frame, and the presence of openings. They observed that both regular and high-strength anchors gave similar results in terms of lateral strength, which was only slightly less than that of a monolithic wall. On the other hand, metallic anchors resulted in slightly lower lateral strength, but much higher ductility. The authors also reported that higher amount of reinforcement resulted in higher strength, but lower ductility; and that the presence of openings did reduce the lateral strength, but their position was found to be insignificant.

Behavior and failure were dominated by flexure, but open, u-shaped FRP jackets at the two edges of the composite wall were essential to prevent premature failure near the base because of poor detailing of the columns. Slippage/separation at interfaces between the web and surrounding frame members was minor for both connection details. In one specimen the critical plastic hinge did not form at the base but instead in a horizontal band defined by the first-storey beam of the frame, in which

the vertical beam stirrups were much weaker than the vertical wall reinforcement; however, this did not adversely affect the global energy-dissipation and deformation capacity

The method has been found to significantly increase the strength and stiffness of the retrofitted frames, even in the case of RC elements with short lap-slices and pre-existing damage [125–127]. The alternative of not infilling the whole bay length has also been explored and it has been reported that the longer the wall, the higher the strength, stiffness and energy dissipation, but also the more prevalent the post-peak strength degradation [128,129]. Strepelias et al. [130] reported that the behaviour of RC frames infilled with RC walls were dominated by flexure, but open, U-shaped FRP jackets at the two edges of the composite wall were essential to prevent premature failure near the base because of poor detailing of the columns.

More recently, Poljanšek et al. [131] performed pseudo-dynamic tests on a full-scale four-storey, three-bay RC building at the European Laboratory for Structural Assessment (ELSA lab, Joint Research Centre, Ispra). The RC infill was constructed within the middle bay, filling its whole length and having the same width (250 mm) as the surrounding columns and beams (Fig. 14). A combination of dowel and starter bars was employed in order to connect the new element to the existing frame. Their distribution was variable along the height of the structure and CFRP U-jackets were constructed at the ground level, at the column bases. The authors reported that the strengthened building was able to sustain a 0.25 g earthquake without any significant damage. Moreover, the connection of the wall behaved satisfactorily. This study concluded that the RC infilling technique is a viable method for seismic retrofitting and can be used in cases the strength and ductility of an existing structure is in need of upgrading.

3.1.2.3. Rocking walls. New RC walls, whether constructed as completely new elements or placed within frames as infills, are supposed to dissipate the seismic energy through the formation of a plastic hinge at their base. Of course, this plastic hinge means that damage, such as concrete cracking, reinforcing steel yielding etc., is expected to occur at these places. Instead of this approach, shear walls can be designed so that uplifting and rocking is permitted at their base. In this case, minimal damage, no strength and stiffness loss and also no residual deformations (through the use of tendons) are expected. Energy dissipation is achieved thanks to the rocking action itself and can be further increased by employing additional dissipating devices. Last, but not least, the corner regions of such a wall have to be reinforced, as the rocking action induces high compressive strains and shear keys must be placed to the wall's end to ensure that no sliding is permitted.

Rocking walls have been investigated both experimentally and analytically. Compared to fixed ones, they have been found to be more effective when overloaded, and provide better protection to the existing elements, thanks to their self-centering characteristics [132,133]. They exhibit less energy dissipation than traditional shear walls, but thanks to their flag-shaped response they result in minimal residual deformations [134].

Fig. 13. Addition of RC walls (a) placed around a column, (b) external to the frame, (c) as buttress.

Fig. 14. Serfin Project: (a) RC infill wall dowels and web reinforcement; (b) Prototype testing [Source: [131]].

Fardis et al. [135] studied numerically the behavior of a four-storey prototype structure as well as of two existing and highly irregular ones, retrofitted with new RC shear walls. They reported that the rocking walls were protected from damage and at the same time did not significantly affect the existing members' behavior in the case of the regular building. However, some existing RC members of the irregular buildings did suffer in shear and flexure, in which case FRP strengthening was proposed. The authors also stated that in case of real-life buildings, the addition of new walls might not always be able to improve their performance, due to high irregularities or appearance and functionality limitations.

For a more detailed treatment of seismic retrofitting with rocking shear walls the reader may refer to Tsonis et al. [98].

3.1.3. Addition/Modification of infills

Unreinforced masonry (URM) is a material commonly used in RC structures to construct infills within the frames, as well as the internal partitions of a building. URM infills have been thoroughly investigated in the past by the academic community as it has been proved that their contribution to the lateral strength and stiffness of a structure is significant. In most cases, this contribution seems to be beneficial, as they function as a weaker version of shear walls. However, when their height-wise or floor-wise positioning is not even or when they are built partially within a bay's height, they can have adverse effects as well. Taking into account the beneficial effects of infills as well as their low construction cost, several researchers have proposed to use them as retrofitting elements. Extra reinforcement, with either traditional or advanced materials, can also be employed to enhance their behavior as well.

3.1.3.1. Unreinforced and lightly reinforced masonry infills. RC frames with URM infills have been reported to have a significantly higher strength and stiffness, when compared to bare ones. Moreover, since the increase in lateral strength is generally higher than the increase of the inertia forces that is caused by their higher stiffness, their contribution is in most cases beneficial [136]. In RC structures with flat-slabs, URM infills have also been found to result in a two-fold increase in the lateral capacity, while at the same time, high drift reversals are achievable [137]. Strengthening and repairing existing masonry infills with light steel wire meshes, embedded in cementitious mortar has also been found to increase their strength and stiffness [138]. Pardalopoulos et al. [139] presented a rapid retrofit design methodology, where masonry infills are utilized for strengthening existing substandard constructions in order for their RC load-bearing elements to behave elastically in the event of the

design earthquake.

3.1.3.2. ECC-strengthened masonry infills. Engineered cementitious composites (ECC) may also be used to strengthen URM infills. These are high performance materials, often reinforced with short fibers and with superior mechanical properties compared to common mortars. When used as an overlay over a masonry infill, they can increase its load-bearing capacity and energy dissipation by more than two times, as observed by Deghani et al. [140]. Steel mesh reinforcement and shear dowels along the frame perimeter can be employed to further enhance the behavior of this technique. Kyriakides and Billington [141] performed small-scale tests on masonry infilled RC frames and concluded that the use of shear dowels can be extremely beneficial; specimens that had them were able to withstand four times higher loads and were also three times stiffer.

3.1.3.3. FRP-strengthened masonry infills. URM infills can significantly increase the strength and stiffness of an RC structure. However, they also experience damage, which is realized through diagonal cracking, even during moderate earthquakes, as their cracking strength is exceeded at low inter-storey drifts, in the order of approximately 0.3%. Therefore, in order to improve the behavior of infills and reduce the likelihood of damage, many researchers have proposed the use of FRP as a means to reinforce them.

FRP-reinforced masonry infills have been reported to increase a frame's strength and ductility, as evidenced by experimental investigations performed in the recent past. When compared to RC infilling, FRP-strengthened infills can achieve similar strength and stiffness gains, but exhibit a much more rapid post-peak degradation [142]. In other studies, FRP-strengthened infills achieved superior seismic performance than the unretrofitted masonry-infilled frames exhibiting significantly higher strength and stiffness (e.g. [143–145]). Other researchers have also pointed out the improvement of the lateral resistance and stiffness, as well as the lower drifts demands during earthquake simulations [146,147].

3.1.3.4. TRM-strengthened masonry infills. As an alternative to FRP, textile reinforced mortars (TRM) can be used as a means to improve the performance of masonry infills and transform them into reliable lateral load resisting elements. Compared to FRP-based solutions discussed above, the TRM strengthening technique provides a plethora of advantages, including:

- Higher compatibility of the overlays with the masonry.
- Easier and more cost-effective application, as no epoxy resins are involved.
- Better fire resistance and performance at elevated temperatures.
- Simultaneous improvement of the out-of-plane behavior of the infill; avoidance of out-of-plane failures.

Koutas et al. [148] investigated experimentally the in-plane behaviour of TRM-strengthened masonry-infilled RC frames and reported a 56% higher lateral strength, 52% higher deformation capacity and 22% higher energy dissipation capacity, compared to the as-built ones. Numerical simulations were also performed by Koutas et al. [149], who also proposed an analytical model to simulate the aforementioned retrofitting scheme. The model was found in excellent agreement with test results, whereas Pohoryles and Bournas [150,151] applied the same modelling approach, namely macro-model with an additional tensile tie to account for the TRM, but calibrated against all available experiments, considering also increased compressive strut. Similar experimental results, namely 50% higher strength and 30% higher stiffness, were reported by Akhouni et al. [152], who performed in-plane cyclic tests on half-scale, single-bay RC infilled frames, strengthened with a glass TRM solution.

TRM jacketing was found very effective both in improving the out-of-plane resistance [153] and the combined in- and out-of-plane response [154,155] of masonry-infilled RC frames. More specifically, Koutas and Bournas [153] reported that the out-of-plane performance was dramatically improved in all cases of retrofitted walls, as the maximum load resisted increased 3.79–5.45 times for single-wythe walls and 2.45 times for the double-wythe walls (Fig. 15). Gkournelos et al. [155] reported that in-plane loaded walls with TRM outperformed significantly their non-retrofitted counterparts, whereas out-of-plane loaded walls with combined TRM/thermal insulation performed much better or at least as good as their TRM-only retrofitted counterparts, for the case with or without prior in-plane damage, respectively.

3.1.3.5. TRM jacketing combined with thermal insulation for integrated retrofitting. More recent studies proposed an integrated seismic and energy retrofitting approach, applied to external building envelopes (e. g. masonry infills) by combining TRM jacketing with thermal insulation. The concept of the combined seismic and energy retrofitting with advanced materials has been investigated experimentally for masonry buildings (Fig. 16a) subjected to out-of-plane or in-plane loading [65,156]. It has also been explored for the concurrent seismic and energy upgrading of RC buildings envelopes (Fig. 16b) in experimental

Fig. 15. Out-of-plane response of TRM-reinforced masonry infills [Source: [153]].

[155] and analytical studies [157–159]. These latter analytical studies, proposed a common approach based on the expected annual loss (of consumed energy or expected seismic loss) which allowed to evaluate the financial feasibility and benefits of the combined approach. It was shown that, for seismic-prone countries, the payback period of the retrofitting intervention could be significantly reduced when seismic is applied concurrently with energy retrofitting by combining advanced construction materials, thanks to large savings related to the labor costs. (See Fig. 17)

3.1.3.6. Precast concrete panels. An alternative way of strengthening RC frames via infilling is by using precast concrete panels (PCP). This technique was first introduced by Higashi et al. [160,161], who used such panels to retrofit RC frames. They observed that a significant increase in the stiffness and strength of the specimens could be achieved. Using this upgrading technique, the authors were able to trigger a ductile failure mode and improve the deformation capacity of the specimens. Other researchers have also employed PCP to strengthen under-designed RC frames and have reported satisfactory strength increase, energy dissipation and in reducing the displacement demands in the case of pseudo-dynamic testing [162–164]. Lately, Akin and Sezer [165] proposed the bonding of PCP on the masonry infill faces and found that the retrofitted specimens exhibited superior strength, stiffness and energy dissipation characteristics. More importantly, they stated that the suggested retrofitting scheme can be applied without the need to evacuate the building.

3.1.3.7. Isolated masonry infills. Tsantilis and Triantafillou [166] developed and verified both experimentally and analytically an innovative technique for improving the performance of infilled RC frames by isolating the infill panels through the use of a highly deformable cellular material (foam) at the interface between masonry infills and the surrounding frame. According to this technique, illustrated in Fig. 16, infilled RC frames behave similarly to bare frames, that is with negligible interaction with the surrounding members, for low to moderate seismic excitations. As drifts become large during strong seismic excitations (near collapse limit state) the cellular materials become fully compressed, and the infill is activated as a diagonal compression strut, thereby providing extra strength and stiffness to the frame-infill system.

3.2. Demand decrease

Retrofitting techniques which aim at increasing a structure's lateral load capacity and stiffness can be employed in most cases and mitigate successfully the seismic risk. However, their applicability is not always possible, for a number of reasons. First, as they generally cause an increase to the lateral stiffness, higher seismic forces are introduced to the structure's body. Even if new elements are designed so that they can cope with these increased demands, the soil beneath the structure might fail and lead to a global overturning failure mechanism. Moreover, the capacity-increase-related techniques do not reduce the floor accelerations experienced by the structures during an earthquake. These accelerations can however lead to the failure of various non-structural elements. Last, but not least, in certain cases where sensitive equipment is to be installed inside buildings, the limitation of any possible floor oscillations is of utmost importance. Hence, an alternative route to increasing structural capacity is the reduction of demand; this may be achieved by using base isolation and/or devices for energy dissipation.

3.2.1. Base isolation

Base isolation aims at decoupling the superstructure from the underlying foundation soil, so that only minimal vibrations are perceived by it during a strong ground motion (Fig. 18). This can be achieved by using isolation systems (elastomeric bearings, lead-rubber bearings, friction-pendulum bearings etc.) which significantly increase the

Fig. 16. Schematic illustration of combined seismic and energy retrofitting system for (a) masonry [Source: [65]] and (b) RC building [Source: [150]] envelopes.

Fig. 17. Schematic illustration of the proposed concept: (a) response of RC frame with isolation using cellular materials; (b) placement of cellular material at the frame-infill interface; and (c) behavior of cellular materials in uniaxial compression [Source: [166]].

structure's natural period. The increased period leads to lower spectral accelerations, thus lower base shear demands. At the same time though, the spectral displacements, for large-period structures, are also higher (Fig. 19). This is why, in many cases, the employed isolator systems also have damping-increasing characteristics or are combined with supplementary dampers.

Base isolation is very effective in reducing the seismic vulnerability of a given structure, however its implementation in the case of existing structures is not a straightforward task. To address this matter, Clemente and De Stefano [167] proposed a seismic isolation procedure which consists of creating an isolated platform under the foundations, without touching the building at all. A set of horizontal pipes are inserted below the foundations and the isolation devices are placed at the horizontal diametric plane. A trench is then formed around the building, thus completing its isolation from the surrounding soil. At the end of the

intervention, both the structure, as well as the ground directly below it are seismically isolated, without having affected at all any architectural characteristic of the former. The authors reported that this isolation scheme is applicable for both historical buildings and industrial plants, in which multiple structures can be isolated at once, thus protecting crucial connecting components; however, it should be noted such a strengthening system is prohibitively expensive for the big majority of the existing buildings.

Briseghella et al. [168] proposed the use of friction pendulum isolation systems as a means to reduce the seismic vulnerability existing RC buildings. The technique comprises of the construction of two new RC slabs, a bottom and a top one, which facilitate the isolation of the superstructure from the foundation using lifting devices. The authors performed numerical simulations on an existing RC building, located in L'Aquila, Italy, which had been severely damaged during the 2009

Fig. 18. Capacity reduction systems: (a) conventional design of RC frame; (b) base isolation; (c) energy dissipation using dampers; (d) tuned mass damper.

Fig. 19. Base isolation principle.

earthquake. A significant reduction of more than four times was reported for both the induced shear forces and the inter-storey drifts, thus validating the applicability of the method.

A combination of CFRP wrapping with base isolation was suggested by Mazza and Pucci [169]. Simulations were performed on a six-storey, 60-year old RC building, which was initially designed to rise five storeys in height. Apart from the original, fixed-base structure, three more retrofitting scenarios were taken into account: (a) shear and flexural strengthening with CFRP, (b) seismic isolation with elastomeric and sliding bearings, and (c) combination of CFRP strengthening with base isolation. Because the initial RC elements lacked shear reinforcement, CFRP strengthening was found to be necessary to satisfy the code requirements, but that alone could not cover the seismic demands. The only scheme, which was found to satisfy all the code requirements, was the one that combined CFRP strengthening with base isolation.

Mazza et al. [170] also performed numerical simulations to assess the effectiveness of base isolation systems on existing RC structures under near-fault earthquakes. A six-storey, hypothetical building was designed according to outdated Italian codes and used in the simulations. Three different systems were accounted for, namely high-damping-laminated-rubber bearings (HDLRBs), in-parallel combination of HDLRBs and sliding bearings (SBs) and friction pendulum bearings (FPBs). All three of them proved to be highly effective in reducing by many times the ductility demands for the existing RC members, compared to the initial, fixed-base structure.

3.2.2. Passive energy dissipation systems

An alternative to base isolation, in the broader area of reducing the

seismic demands of a given structure, is the installation of passive energy dissipation systems. The role of these devices is to dissipate the largest percentage of the input seismic energy, so that the remaining structural elements remain undamaged. Different options exist and can be applied on both the existing and new RC structures. A brief overview of the available passive energy dissipation systems is given below.

An effective way to increase energy dissipation is by using metallic yield dampers. This scheme mainly consists of eccentric Λ -braces (see Fig. 18c and also Section 3.1.1), which are connected to the beam via thin steel plates. Through the yielding of these plates, large amounts of energy are dissipated. However, these systems need regular inspection and should also be replaced after large earthquakes that may cause their fracture.

Lee and Kim [171] developed a box-shaped steel slit damper for the seismic strengthening of structures. The authors performed experiments on two damper specimens and numerical simulations of an existing RC structure. They reported that the proposed dampers were effective in dissipating large percentages of the seismic input energy and the RC frame members remained almost all elastic.

Oinam and Sahoo [172] recently performed an experimental and analytical investigation on the use of metallic dampers as a means to improve the seismic performance of soft-storey RC frames (Figure 41). They reported that the proposed retrofitting scheme was effective in improving the lateral strength, stiffness, energy dissipation and the drift capacity of the tested RC frame.

Viscoelastic dampers consist of thin steel plates combined with viscoelastic material laminates. These materials are able to withstand the high shear strains, which develop during strong earthquakes and

that way dissipate large amounts of the seismic energy. Such devices are normally installed at the connection points of metallic braces, therefore they can be employed along with a bracing system of a broader seismic retrofitting scheme.

Friction dampers rely on the friction developed between specially treated steel plates, which are clamped in contact using high strength bolts. Relative slip occurs at a predefined load, which is selected so that it is not exceeded under the wind loading cases. The hysteresis loops of these dampers are rectangular, thus resulting in large amounts of energy dissipation and protecting the structural elements. This type of dampers is also installed within bracing systems.

Valente [173] investigated through numerical analyses the use of friction dampers as a means to improve the seismic performance of existing precast RC buildings, constructed without seismic provisions having their long-span roof girders imply supported on column corbels or forks (see e.g. [174]). The dampers are selectively positioned at beam-column joints in order to provide a moment connection, capable of large energy dissipation. The author reported a significant increase in the dissipating capacity of buildings. Moreover, plastic deformations were concentrated within the friction dampers, protecting that way columns from severe damage.

Viscous-fluid dampers achieve energy dissipation through the movement of a piston with small slits inside a highly viscous fluid of oily nature. During strong earthquakes, the pistons that are placed as braces within frames start to move, so that the viscous fluid is forced to flow through the tiny cavities. This results in large amounts of dissipated energy and effectively reduces the forces experienced by the structural members (e.g. [175]).

Different types of passive damping mechanisms are the tuned mass dampers (TMD), see Fig. 16d. Initially they were used to mitigate wind-induced excitations, but they have also been used in the field of earthquake engineering. TMD are tuned to a specific frequency which is chosen to coincide with the structure's fundamental frequency, so they can be most effective in reducing the dynamic response quantities [176]. An alternative to TMD are **tuned liquid dampers**, which work using the same principle and also have lower cost [176].

3.2.3. Active and hybrid energy dissipation systems

Active and hybrid control systems are force delivery devices consisting of real-time sensors and signal processing controllers. These force delivery devices are normally actuators controlling braces, mass dampers or affecting the structure's stiffness and damping properties. Active control systems require a continuous external power source, a failure of which would lead to the failure of the system. Hybrid systems, on the other hand, combine passive energy dissipation devices along with the active system, so that their power needs are lower, and a possible cut-off would not render the system completely inactive. Such systems have been used only in limited cases as seismic retrofitting schemes; their major applications are found in new high-rise buildings.

Priya and Gopalakrishnan [177] proposed a damping enhancement-based seismic retrofitting technique for damaged RC structures using a mass driver along with a magnetorheological damper (MR-MD). The authors performed experiments on a three-storey RC frame structure, equipped with a MR-MD system, in order to investigate the effect of the electric current input to the response. The authors suggested to use a suboptimum frequency tuning to account for the stiffness degradation that occurs in RC structures. Moreover, high currents were found to be counterproductive, as they resulted in the mass damper acting as a rigid body. A reduction of 50% in the spectral accelerations was reported by the authors.

TMD along with oil dampers were recently used in Japan for the seismic retrofitting of a high-rise RC building against high-period earthquakes [178]. The oil dampers employed stroke control functions to increase their damping in case the TMD velocity would reach a predefined level. Both numerical simulations and structural monitoring were used to evaluate the behavior of the retrofitting scheme. The

authors reported that significant reduction in the structural response was recorded thanks to the applied retrofitting scheme.

4. Conclusions

Addressing the problem of the poor performance of structures during past earthquakes, the field of seismic upgrading of existing RC buildings has received great attention both in the academic world and in engineering practice; and very recently also by EU policies (European Green Deal, Renovation Wave) supporting an integrated (e.g. seismic and energy) retrofitting approach. This paper outlined the seismic upgrading methods that have been developed for application in RC buildings, emphasizing on novel approaches. Both local and global techniques were discussed and assessed in terms of their strengths and weaknesses.

Local retrofitting measures are usually employed when the examined building already has an acceptable level of lateral strength and stiffness. Most common applications include the jacketing of RC beams and columns aiming at increasing their shear strength, available ductility and avoiding lap-slice and buckling failures. Both traditional (concrete and steel) and novel (FRP and TRM) jacketing materials were analyzed, putting more emphasis on the latter. Specifically, FRP have been used successfully in many experimental campaigns as well as real-world applications. They are also corrosion-free and do not affect the elements dimensions and stiffness, as opposed to RC and steel jackets. On the other hand, their poor behavior in high temperatures calls for extra fire-safety measures. TRM offer a promising alternative to FRP, as jacketing materials. They have slightly reduced effectiveness, but are more economic, easy to install and have superior fire resistance.

Global structural retrofitting techniques, both capacity-increasing and demand-decreasing, were also thoroughly discussed. Concerning the former, steel braces, RC shear walls and infills were examined; all these yield a significant increase in a building's lateral strength and stiffness. Steel braces are a very effective means of providing extra strength and stiffness to an existing structure. Eccentric braces offer significant energy dissipation capabilities, while buckling-restrained ones can be employed to avoid buckling failures in the compression members. The addition of RC shear walls, either as new elements or by infilling of existing frames, can also be beneficial for the seismic strengthening of structures. Still, different failure modes need to be considered, depending on the initial deficiencies of the as-built structure. Rocking walls have proved to be very promising, as they suffer minimal damage and can be combined with energy-dissipating devices to further control the structural response. Lastly, masonry infills consist a very economical way of increasing a structure's lateral strength and stiffness. When strengthened using FRP, TRM or reinforced mortar overlays, they form a reliable lateral load resisting mechanism. Precast concrete panels can also be used as frame infills, and result in similar beneficial results. Integrated seismic and energy upgrading can be provided in some of the global seismic retrofitting measures reviewed (e.g. by combining TRM, exoskeleton systems, PCPs, RC/masonry infilling with thermal insulation).

A relatively more advanced approach to the issue of structural retrofitting is through decreasing the seismic demands. Within this area, seismic isolation as well as passive, active and hybrid energy dissipation systems can be employed to effectively reduce the seismically induced vibrations on a given structure. Due to the generally higher cost and complicated nature of such retrofitting schemes, relatively limited applications can be found in the literature and in engineering practice. Nevertheless, in cases of retrofitting important structures or when vibration control is of outmost importance, such methods can yield extremely good results.

Selecting the appropriate retrofitting solution for a given structure is a multiparametric problem without a one-fits-all solution. The specific details of the examined structure, the desired level of performance upgrade, the availability of materials, specialized personnel etc., and of course, the overall intervention cost need to be accounted for. Moreover,

the design of such retrofitting measures usually calls for advanced simulations. Therefore, it is important that engineers have a robust regulatory framework to follow, so that their designs can be reliable.

A regulatory framework for the design of the seismic retrofitting of RC structures with novel materials and techniques does not exist today, with the exception of EN 1998–3, which covers (only partially) FRPs for the enhancement of the shear capacity of columns and walls, for the enhancement of the available ductility at beam or column ends through added confinement, and for the prevention of lap splice failures through increased lap confinement. It is hoped that the upcoming generation two of the Eurocodes (to be launched within the coming years) will play some role with respect to that matter. To the best of the author's knowledge, the upcoming version of EN 1998–3 will include revised models for FRP retrofitting, but other novel techniques, as discussed in this report, do not seem to be covered, despite the fact that research has already advanced substantially, and certainly more than for the case of traditional techniques, such as RC and steel jacketing. This is a gap that needs to be filled.

According to the authors' view, research gaps with regards to seismic upgrading of RC structures with novel techniques are minor. An area, which is certainly worth receiving further attention by the scientific community, is the integration of today's modern seismic upgrading techniques with measures for energy upgrading, and possibly with low cost – yet reliable – systems for smart monitoring.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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